

Circularity in manufacturing of prefabricated houses

Manufacturing prefabricated houses with a circular approach represents a sophisticated concept. As an example, the insulation material generated from sawdust in the production process can be processed into a complex and yet profitable product reinforcing resource and energy savings.

High degree of prefabrication, integrating the drying processes, improving accuracy of the processes, speeding-up the installation phase, and guaranteeing safety of the final product are all key factors that strengthen the competitiveness of wood construction. It enlarges the capacity to build eco-and energy positive houses.

Why is it a good practice?

- ▶ Prefabricated houses offer great possibility for enhanced use of wood as a replacement of other construction materials with higher environmental impacts by allowing significant material savings, waste reduction, and reuse of components in wood construction
- ▶ Recycled material use provides high circularity advancement with improved raw material use and availability of side streams for production of components such as wooden insulation panels
- ▶ It demonstrates a sustainable solution with reduced emissions and a long lifetime of wood-based buildings due to better recycling options
- ▶ Improves consumer awareness of more sustainable prefabricated housing options
- ▶ Legislative situation fosters the use of prefabricated wooden houses around Europe

Regional coverage and transferability

A market feasibility study for Northern- and Central Europe predicts a huge market for prefabricated houses (before Covid-19 Pandemic situation). However, since the price-quality ratio and brand perception is considered as the most essential buying criteria, the transferability can be traced to all macroregions.

